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ENTREPRENEURSHIP SKILLS AND ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT IN ENUGU STATE

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14781485>

Abstract: The study examined the entrepreneurship skills on economic development in Enugu state, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to: determine the extent to which financial skills have affected employment generation in Enugu state, Nigeria and examine the effect of networking skills have on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria. The study adopted survey research design; Taro Yamani's formula was used to determine the sample size of 338 with a valid number of 298. The study found that financial skills have strong positive effect on employment generation in Enugu state, Nigeria, revealed through the SPSS version, that correlation coefficient (R) of 0.736 and p-value (0.000) which is less than 0.05 level of significance and the result from hypotheses II, show the correlation coefficient (R) of 0.605 and the p-value (0.001) which is less than 0.05 level of significance, that networking skills have positive effect on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria. The study concluded that entrepreneurship skills have positive effect on economic development in Enugu state, Nigeria. The study recommended that Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) owners should always engage themselves in seminars as to improve their financial skills or have financial skills idea in order to promote employment generation or self-reliance in terms of starting up a business of their own and networking skills had really helped in our country today to reduce poverty from our societies. This is the reason why networking skills should be always be used in any community or group of people because it reduces the poverty rate in a society or country by people coming together, forming goals and bringing resources together used in creating businesses and employment such as cooperative society.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship skills, Economic development, Financial skills, Employment generation, Networking skills & Poverty reduction.

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background of the Study

Entrepreneurship skills play a vital role in fostering economic development in any country, region, including Enugu State in Nigeria. Enugu State, like many other regions, benefit from the cultivation and promotion of

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entrepreneurship skills (Bartik, 2020). Entrepreneurship skills under economic development provide employment generation, networking skills together and infrastructure facilities and Support Systems, simultaneously reduces poverty in the country. Entrepreneurs play a key role in any economy, using the skills and initiative necessary to anticipate needs and bringing good new ideas to market. Entrepreneurship that proves to be successful in taking on the risks of creating a startup is rewarded with profits, fame, and continued growth opportunities. Entrepreneurship that fails results in losses and less prevalence in the markets for those involved (Hasbullahetal, 2022). While the prospect of becoming your own boss and raking in a fortune is alluring to entrepreneurial dreamers, the possible downside to hanging one's own shingle is vast. There are many entrepreneurship skills, entrepreneurial can used to start or developed an existing business, but this paper will be discussing few of them like, creative thinking skills, communication and active listening skills, problem-solving skills; financial skills and networking skills.

Economic development is a drives that transform every society in a country, is visible in employment and wealth generation, stimulation of indigenou entrepreneurship or promotion of entrepreneurial culture/knowledge (Levine, 2018). Just like every states in Nigeria, Enugu state is not exceptional, entrepreneurship as contributed in a large portion to the economic development of Nigeria. Moreover, studies by UNIDO-Nigeria, 2012 show that Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) has the propensity to drive the Nigerian Economy, and data reveal that there are currently over 17 million MSMEs employing over 31 million Nigerians. MSMEs account for over 80% of enterprises that employ about 75 % of the Nigeria's total workforce, and therefore formulating and effectively implementing MSMEs friendly policies represents innovative ways of building the capacity to engage in entrepreneurial activities and creating job opportunities thus, playing a central and invaluable role in helping Nigeria realize its quantity advantage (Pollin, and Baker, 2018). Entrepreneurship skills is significant to entrepreneur and entrepreneurship, because without the knowledge/skills it will be difficulty to carried out entrepreneurship, as said when you are not informed then, you deform. These papers examine the entrepreneurship skills and economic development in Enugu state, Nigeria.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

If Nigeria where to be economic development country, then the need for entrepreneurship skills is necessary or important in the country, but the current situation in Nigeria now shows that the economic development of Nigeria lacks many factors that should help the Nigerian economy to go further such as lack of financial skills, lack of networking skills, critical thinking skills, communication and active listening skills, and problem-solving skills, etc. and this factors have led to the consequences of high unemployment rate and increase in poverty rate also in the country. However, these papers work examined "the entrepreneurship skills on economic development in Enugu state, Nigeria".

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to examine the entrepreneurship skills on economic development in Enugu state, Nigeria. While the specific objectives are to:

- i. Determine the extent to which financial skills have affected employment generation in Enugu state, Nigeria
- ii. Examine the effect of networking skills on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria

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1.4 Research Questions

- i. To what extent does financial skills have effected employment generation in Enugu state, Nigeria?
- ii. What was the effect of networking skills on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria?

1.5 Statement of Hypotheses

- i. H₀: Financial skills do not have effect on employment generation in Enugu state, Nigeria.
- ii. H₀: Networking skills does not have effect on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

1.6 Scope of the Study

The content scope of this work covered entrepreneurship skills and economic development, with focus on financial skills to employment generation and networking skills to poverty reduction

While the study was carried out in Enugu state of Nigeria as the geographical scope.

1.7 Significance of the Study

General Public: This research work is beneficial to the people of Enugu state and to Nigerians in general, by passing the information about entrepreneurship skills and its benefits on economic development.

Research Material: This research study serves as reference material to related research topics to libraries and institutions also is a contribution to knowledge for the researcher.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

2.1 Conceptual Review

2.1.2 Entrepreneurship

Entrepreneurship is the process of running a business using a new idea or in a different way, which ultimately helps the buyer or the customer. The new ideas in a business can be in the form of a unique product or service. A different way of doing business makes an entrepreneur different (Jacobs, Lucia, and Lester, 2020). A traditional business person runs his venture like most others. Whereas an entrepreneur uses unique ways of doing business be it reaching out to the customers through marketing and advertising, new ideas or new ways to meet customer needs or running the operations in a more efficient way. In this module, the focus is on helping you to understand what are the different values and attitudes of an entrepreneur which makes them successful (Amobi, 2022). To nurture entrepreneurial development, small and medium scale enterprise operators or entrepreneurs are being considered as main sustenance of the economy development drive, because of their capacity in enhancing the economy productivity and standard of living of the common man, as they account for over 50 percent of GDP of developing economies (Eichler and Schwartz, 2019). However, lack of access to relative cheap and effective source of finance have been identified as the major factor hindering their contribution to economic growth in developing countries like Nigeria.

A great entrepreneur must be able to effectively communicate, sell, focus, learn, and strategize. An ability to continuously learn is not just a key entrepreneurial skill, but also a very valuable life skill. Growing a business requires a sound strategy based on inherent business sense and skills (Rothstein, 2023). Entrepreneurs play a key role in any economy, using the skills and initiative necessary to anticipate needs and bringing good new ideas to market. Entrepreneurship that proves to be successful in taking on the risks of creating a startup is rewarded with profits, fame, and continued growth opportunities (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020). Entrepreneurship that fails results in losses and less prevalence in the markets for those involved (Hasbullahetal, 2022). While the prospect of becoming your own boss and raking in a fortune is alluring to entrepreneurial

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dreamers, the possible downside to hanging one's own shingle is vast. Income isn't guaranteed, employer-sponsored benefits go by the wayside, and when your business loses money, your personal assets can take a hit; not just a corporation's bottom line. But adhering to a few tried and true principles can go a long way in diffusing risk (Ile, 2013).

Components of Entrepreneurial Skills

Financial skills: The ability to handle resources, assess investments, calculate ROI is a must for entrepreneurs. Apart from this, they must know how to use accounting and budgeting software to keep track of all the financial processes. By learning financial skills, entrepreneurs avoid overspending and optimally allocate resources (Lubna, 2019).

Networking skills: Networking involves building and managing relationship with other professionals to grow and promote a business. Effective networking skills open up future opportunities and help build a solid brand. Networking allows entrepreneurs to meet like-minded professionals, build future teams and stay up-to-date with industry trends. It is one of the most desirable skills for entrepreneurs because, through a solid network, they can meet professionals to fund their ideas, access professional business expertise and get feedback on their new venture or idea (Kuada, 2018).

Critical thinking skills: Critical thinking is an entrepreneur skill that objectively analyses the information and draws a rational conclusion. It helps entrepreneurs assess a situation and come up with a logical solution. Employers look for candidates with critical thinking because it helps solve problems and build strategies for business growth. Usually, a critical thinker is independent, competent and reflective. This skill helps entrepreneurs logically connect ideas, scrutinize information, evaluate arguments, find inconsistencies in work and solve complex issues. Instead of memorizing information, such candidates use the information to deduce meaningful insights (Kuada, 2018).

Communication and active listening skills: Every entrepreneur must be able to communicate effectively with clients, team members and all other stakeholders. Whether through verbal communication during meetings or sending reports and messages through emails about the project, entrepreneurs require superior written and verbal communication. Apart from communication skills, entrepreneurs must be excellent listeners to understand the project's requirement and discussion during project meetings (Nattavud, 2021).

Problem-solving skills: Often, entrepreneurs face challenging and unexpected situations. It could be a venture capitalist refusing further funding or a team member refusing to work as per the project guidelines; an entrepreneur must possess excellent problem-solving skills to handle stressful situations and calmly identify alternate solutions. Exceptional problem-solving skills ensure they reach their business goal (Kuada, 2018).

2.1.3 Economic Development

In the economics study of the public sector, economic and social development is the process by which the economic well-being and quality of life of a nation, region, local community, or an individual are improved according to targeted goals and objectives (UN, 2017). The term has been used frequently in the 20th and 21st centuries, but the concept has existed in the West for far longer. "Modernization", "Westernization", and especially "industrialization" are other terms often used while discussing economic development (Josephine et al., 2021). Historically, economic development policies focused on industrialization and infrastructure; since the 1960s, it has increasingly focused on poverty reduction. Whereas economic development is a policy intervention aiming to improve the well-being of people, economic growth is a phenomenon of

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market productivity and increases in GDP; economist Amartya Sen describes economic growth as but "one aspect of the process of economic development" (Evans et al., 2021).

The precise definition of economic development has been contested: while economists in the 20th century viewed development primarily in terms of economic growth, sociologists instead emphasized broader processes of change and modernization (N-Power, 2020). Development and urban studies scholar Karl Seidman summarizes economic development as "a process of creating and utilizing physical, human, financial, and social assets to generate improved and broadly shared economic well-being and quality of life for a community or region" (Umar, 2011). Daphne Greenwood and Richard Holt distinguish economic development from economic growth on the basis that economic development is a "broadly based and sustainable increase in the overall standard of living for individuals within a community", and measures of growth such as per capita income do not necessarily correlate with improvements in quality of life. The United Nations Development Programme in 1997 defined development as increasing peoples choices (Arnold, 2013). Choices depend on the people in question and their nation. The UNDP indicates four chief factors in development, especially human development, which are empowerment, equity, productivity and sustainability.

2.1.4 Components of Economic Development

2.1.4.1 Employment Generation

The process by which number of employment in an organization, is increased. He came to power with job creation at the top of his agenda, but the new government has failed to get people back to work (Blanchet-Cohen, & Salazar, 2019). Job Creation means a net increase in the number of employees directly employed in an enterprise compared with the average over the previous 12 months. Any job lost during that 12-month period has to be deducted from the number of jobs created during the same period. The amount of aid cannot exceed a certain percentage of the salary costs of the person employed, calculated over a period of two years. The percentage is equal to the intensity allowed under the conditions and procedures regulated by law for granting employment aid (Wark, 2016).

Jobs growth refers to the net increase in the number of nonfarm payrolls during the previous month. This number is widely followed because employment is crucial for economic performance (Kalagbor & Harry, 2019). A 2016 analysis by the Federal Reserve Bank of San Francisco estimated a monthly increase of between 50,000 and 110,000 nonfarm payrolls to be the steady-state jobs growth rate that is in line with the gradual expansion of the labor force. Bigger gains suggest growth above the trend, while smaller ones or outright losses may signal a slowdown (Kalagbor & Harry, 2019). That said, it is important to remember that the jobs growth numbers in the Employment Situation Summary are estimates. The numbers for a given month are revised in each of the next two monthly reports based on additional survey submissions. A monthly nonfarm payroll increase of about 130,000 is considered statistically significant (Ledford, Lucas, Dairsagh & Ravelli, 2013).

2.1.4.2 Poverty Reduction

Poverty reduction, poverty relief, or poverty alleviation is a set of measures, both economic and humanitarian, that are intended to permanently lift people out of poverty. Information and communication technologies for development help to fight poverty (National Bureau of Statistics, 2020). Poverty reduction, poverty relief, or poverty alleviation is a set of measures, both economic and humanitarian, that are intended to permanently lift people out of poverty (Ahmed and McQuaid, 2015). Measures, like those promoted by Henry George in his economics classic *Progress and Poverty*, are those that raise, or are intended to raise, ways of enabling the poor to create wealth for themselves as a conduit of ending poverty forever. In modern times, various economists within the Georgism movement propose measures like the land value tax to enhance access to the natural world for all (Amobi, 2022). Poverty occurs in both developing countries and developed countries. While poverty is

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much more widespread in developing countries, both types of countries undertake poverty reduction measures. Poverty has been historically accepted in some parts of the world as inevitable as non-industrialized economies produced very little, while populations grew almost as fast, making wealth scarce (Eichler and Schwartz, 2019). Poverty has since been a serious challenge to governments in Nigeria. Its effects which include lack and deprivation in the basic necessities of life are worrisome (Cray et al., 2018). Poverty humiliates and dehumanizes its victim as (Blanchet-Cohen & Salazar, 2019) rightly noted. Nigeria as the “Giant of Africa” Has been humiliated and dehumanized. Poverty as a serious issue in Nigeria can be defined as the condition of having insufficient resources or income. In its most extreme form, poverty is lack of basic needs such as adequate nutrition food, clothing, housing, clean water and health services (Arnold, 2017).

The increasing incidence of poverty, both within and among locations, was in spite of various resources and efforts exerted on poverty related programmes and schemes in the country, thus suggesting that the programmes and schemes were ineffective and ineffectual. In the light of this, there is a need to review ICT and how ICT can make the various programmes and scheme effective and effectual as stipulated. This paper studies the impact of ICT and its effects on poverty alleviation and then provides adequate recommendations on the matter (Umar, 2018).

ICT can empower small scale to medium scale enterprises (SMES). IT has become, indispensable for all kinds of business. SME increases, competition increases which often result to results to a decrease in prices and customers (Blanchet-Cohen & Salazar, 2019). This will in turn erode existing profits, creating less incentive for people to start SME. 1. IT impact can also improve the core business of SME in every step of business process. IT has enabled the establishment of SMEs as their presence on the internet and used it to communicate with suppliers and customers to search for business information and advertisement. 2. ICT can be used for wealth creation; some trained IT engineers, scientists, technicians and software developers can develop software made in Nigeria another services to earn foreign exchange. This additional foreign exchange earnings generated can expand indigenous IT products and services. 3. ICT can create job opportunities: ICT can empower Nigeria Youth with IT Skills to participate in Software and IT development thereby creating job opportunities and making their job lucrative. This can eradicate or at least minimize poverty in the country (Evans et al., 2021).

2.1.5 Conceptual Framework

This section below show the framework of the entrepreneurship skills on economic development in Enugu state, Nigeria, with respect to the dependent and independent variables involves in the paper work.

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Source: Researcher's Model, 2024

2.2 Theoretical Framework

This section contained the various theories involved in this researched work.

2.2.1 Human Capital Theory

Human capital theory is an economic concept that emphasizes the role of human capital in the production process and economic growth. Developed by economists such as Gary Becker in the 1960s and was published in 1961s, human capital theory posits that investments in education, training, healthcare, and other forms of human development contribute significantly to an individual's productivity and earning potential. Human capital theory has been influential in shaping policies related to education, training, healthcare, and labor market interventions. This theory posits that entrepreneurial skills and capabilities are forms of human capital that contribute to economic development. Human capital includes attributes such as education, skills, knowledge, and entrepreneurial mindset. Individuals with higher levels of human capital are better equipped to recognize opportunities, start businesses, and drive innovation, thus stimulating economic growth.

2.2.2 Resource-Based View (RBV) of Entrepreneurship

The Resource-Based View (RBV) of entrepreneurship is a theoretical framework that emphasizes the role of resources in shaping the competitive advantage and success of entrepreneurial ventures. Originally developed within the field of strategic management by scholars such as Jay Barney and Birger Wernerfelt, trace back to 1980s and early 1990s, RBV posits that a firm's competitive advantage and performance are primarily determined by the unique bundle of resources and capabilities it possesses. The RBV focuses on the role of entrepreneurial resources, capabilities, and competencies in driving economic development. According to this perspective, entrepreneurs leverage their unique resources, such as knowledge, networks, and financial capital, to create value and generate sustainable competitive advantages. By effectively managing and deploying these resources, entrepreneurs can spur economic growth and development.

Briefly this seminar was ankle on two theories (Human Capital theory and Resource-Based View (RBV) of entrepreneurship). Human Capital theory, in practice, show that entrepreneurial skills and capabilities are forms of human capital that contributes to economic development. Human capital includes attributes such as education, skills, knowledge, and entrepreneurial mindset. Individuals with higher levels of human capital are better equipped to recognize opportunities, start businesses, and drive innovation, thus stimulating economic growth. While the Resource-Based View (RBV) of entrepreneurship (RBV) focuses on the role of entrepreneurial resources, capabilities, and competencies in driving economic development. According to this perspective, entrepreneurs leverage their unique resources, such as knowledge, networks, and financial capital, to create value and generate sustainable competitive advantages. By effectively managing and deploying these resources, entrepreneurs can spur economic growth and development. These two theories are important to this seminar topic "Entrepreneurship Skills on Economic Development in Enugu state, Nigeria"

2.3 Empirical Review

2.3.1 Financial Skills and Employment Generation in Nigeria

Orji and Ahungwa (2020) examine the effects of sales promotion on the consumer buying behavior of food seasoning among Nigerian households using Nestle Nigeria Plc Maggi NAIJA POT brand as a case study. The study employed cross sectional research design and the population consists of consumers of Nestle product

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(Maggi seasoning) in Bwari Area Council, Abuja. The sample size is 246 determined using Topman's formula. Primary data was used through administration of questionnaire and regression analysis was used to test the relationship between the study variables. The findings revealed that most of the consumers enjoy the rebates which influence their decision before, during and after the purchase; there is a positive effect of free trial and free gift on consumer buying behavior of Maggi NAIJAPOT in Bwari Area Council, Abuja.

Evans et al. (2021). Write on job creation and youth empowerment in Nigeria, 2011 – 2020. The role of job creation in enhancing youth empowerment cannot be underestimated. This informed why some countries of the world strive to create enabling business environments to support job creation, while another country like Nigeria has put up several social investment programmes that are believed to be geared towards job creation for youth empowerment. The above doubt on how best job creation can benefit the greatest numbers of Nigerian youths for empowerment informed this study. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to investigate those job creation activities that promote youth empowerment for the greatest number of youths. The study intends to provide an answer to the following research questions: 1) Do social investment programmes bring about sustained youth empowerment? 2) Does the provision of enabling business environment bring about youth development? The research method for the study is the qualitative research method, where an interview was used as an instrument of data collection along with secondary sources of data. Thus, interviews were conducted using a convenient sampling technique. The interviews were transcribed in addition to the content analysis that was employed as a technique of data analysis. The following are findings of the study: The duration under consideration has witnessed tremendous social investment programme from 2011 and 2020, however, the level of unemployment and underemployment have continued to witness steady and continuous increase; It was also discovered that one of the challenges hindering effective job creation in the country is the poor state of infrastructure in the country. Implications for society: There is a need for federal and state governments to focus on agricultural infrastructures like modern storage system and tractors. Secondly, federal and state governments should ensure massive infrastructural development like road, electricity, health and education so that job creation can be a reality.

Nattavud (2021) Entrepreneurship education and training are essential for female entrepreneurs who juggle family expectations, personal life, and new ventures at the same time. Indeed, generic entrepreneurship training may fail to promote understanding in gender literacy and its relationship with creating and managing business entities. To help address gender gaps, this article explores gender issues in the training process for female entrepreneurs, the researcher collected primary data from 28 trainers through personal interviews and secondary data from the 43 training evaluation forms from trainees who participated in the national entrepreneurship training programs in Thailand. The researcher identifies three themes that are related to gender gaps and effectiveness in the entrepreneurship training context. They include (1) gender mainstreaming, (2) gender-sensitive training approaches, and (3) the adoption of proper technology and innovation for female entrepreneurs. Secondary data also confirm that female entrepreneurs in this study address the need for professional development that promotes them to engage in gender competencies, technology, and innovation for new ventures. The opportunity for professional development can be limited by family and social commitments. Engaging with experienced female entrepreneurs and business role models can promote understanding in the three areas among female entrepreneurs. This article outlines a novel approach in synergizing gender issues,

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training, and entrepreneurship skills. It concludes with some explanations of the relative efficacy of entrepreneurship training that reduces gender gaps for female entrepreneurs.

Galbraith (2021) states that advertising has an effect on the rising sales of brand product categories and therefore increases the profit of the product. In a study undertaken to find out the role of social status in decision process, Kassarijian et.al. (1995) stated that increased social interaction permits the more rapid spread of new ideas and that there is a relationship between advertising appeals and social character. It may be necessary to mention that marketing activities are interwoven and no one's activities are in stage and except one stage is completed the company may not go over to the next stage. This has resulted in people seeing marketing as an integrated system.

Hasbullah, Iffat, Asmat and Siti (2022) studies Entrepreneurship and Sustainable Development Goals: A Multigroup Analysis of the Moderating Effects of Entrepreneurship Education on Entrepreneurial Intention. The role of entrepreneurs in attaining Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is paramount. Entrepreneurs with strong awareness and commitment to sustainable development help to attain almost all SDGs, as they create businesses that will help employment, eliminate poverty, provide decent work and economic growth, help to reduce hunger, assist in attaining good health and wellbeing, help to achieve affordable and clean energy, and enhance their industries. Realizing the importance of entrepreneurs and entrepreneurship, the government of Malaysia has taken proactive actions to develop and inculcate the entrepreneurial mindset through entrepreneurship education at higher education. This study aims to apply the Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) to analyze the effect of an entrepreneurship course on entrepreneurial intentions of the engineering students at University Teknologi Petron as, as entrepreneurial intention is effective in predicting behavior. A quantitative technique and descriptive cross-sectional study have been employed to collect data. The result of this study indicates that the TPB explains and predicts the entrepreneurial intention. However, the Multigroup Analysis (MGA) results show that attending the entrepreneurship course does not increase the strength of the relationship between the exogenous and endogenous construct compared to those who do not attend the course. The results of this study raise a positive implication toward the improvement of the course curriculum and the teaching pedagogy. An in-depth qualitative study to understand the issue will help to improve the curriculum and pedagogy of entrepreneurship education, and eventually enable a realization of the government's aspirations.

2.3.2 Networking Skills and Poverty Reduction in Nigeria

Agbeja, Adelokun and Akinyemi (2015) conducted Analysis of the Effect of Advertising on Sales and Profitability of Company. The paper assessed the effect of advertising on sales and profitability of a company. The SPSS software package was used to adequately verify the data collected for this study. The regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis of the variables that were involved in this study in order to analyze the data. The paper concludes that there exists a significant relationship between marketing expenses and profitability of the firm and also there exists a significant relationship between turnover and marketing expenses of the firm. The paper suggests that a company should maintain a cost effective system of advertising in which high quality personnel is a major component. The advertising system should be controlled by a mechanism that fosters the good reputation of the company and its product(s).

Ya-Ping (2017) examined the Effects of Sales Promotion on Consumer Involvement and Purchase Intention in Tourism Industry. Sales Promotion has been the routine marketing of businesses appealing consumers to

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making orders and increasing media exposure in recent years. Sales Promotion is a tactic for the sales of goods with price or non-price discounts. There are various sales promotions in the market, but not all of them are effective in marketing, as brand image, perceived value, and purchase intention are also associated. Sales Promotion therefore has become a primary issue for marketing. Aiming at 2014 Kaohsiung International Travel Fair, 1000 copies of questionnaires are distributed to the customers, and 421 valid copies are retrieved, with the retrieval rate 42%. The research results present the significant correlations between sales promotion and consumer involvement, consumer involvement and purchase intention, and sales promotion and purchase intention.

Pembi, Fudamu and Ibrahim (2017) studied the impact of sales promotional strategies on organizational performance in Nigeria. The objectives of this study are to examine the impact of sales promotional strategies on organizational performance with reference to Flour Mills Maiduguri, Borno State Nigeria. The population of this study was carved out of the entire staff of the Flour Mills of Nigeria Maiduguri, Borno State branch cutting across the Top, Middle and lower level management. The study employed both the primary and secondary sources of data collection. Questionnaires were administered to twenty (20) staff using random sampling techniques. The data collected were subjected to descriptive statistics such as percentage analysis in order to analyze the data and regression analyses were used for testing hypotheses. The result signifies that sales promotional strategies have positive and significant effects on organizational performance.

Sanjeet, Gagan and Mandeep (2018) write on the Causal Effect of Advertisement on Profit and Sales. Introduction – The present study evaluates the relationship between advertisement expenditure, sales revenue and the profits of companies, which are listed in the National Stock Exchange (NSE). Originality – In the past researchers evaluated the impact of sales on advertisement or sales. The present research will study the impact of the advertisement expenditure, sales revenue and the profits on each other. There is a need of this study Research Method – The tools used for the analysis are descriptive statistics, unit root test, granger causality, VAR (Vector Auto Regression) and Variance Decomposition. Findings – The findings of the research shows that there is a visible impact of the previous year's sales on the sale of current year as well as the sale impact the advertisement and profit as well. On the other hand, the profit impacts the advertisement.

Aryal (2018) examined sales promotion adopted by Nepalese business organizations and its effects on sales of soft drink in Kathmandu valley. This study is based on the primary data through convenience sampling technique. The primary data collected from the different places of Kathmandu valley by face to face field survey of 150 respondents. It is found that the sales promotion activities play positive impact on sales of soft drink brands. It is believed that the findings of this study may facilitate the Nepalese business organizations for formulating policies of sales promotion on sales of soft drinks products.

Uloko (2019) assessed the impact of promotion on the profitability of the Nigeria Bottling Company Plc, Enugu Plant. The population of the study was made up of 56 management staff drawn from marketing, sales and accounting/finance departments of the company. Employing a census technique, the whole population of 56 management staff constituted the sample size of the study and data obtained from the 56 copies of the questionnaire were presented using descriptive statistics whereas, multiple regression analysis with the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) was conducted to test both the company's financial statement from the year 2003 to 2012 and the hypotheses. The findings from data analysis of company's financial

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statement shows that, profit is slightly influenced by the variables of sales income not necessary cost of promotion, while the results of the hypotheses testing indicated that, rebates have no significant impact on profitability; sales promotion has a significant impact on profitability; personal selling has no significant impact on profitability; public relations have a significant impact on profitability. The need for an organization to properly coordinate its promotional strategies to achieve a clear consistent and competitive message about itself and its products has become an issue of concern to every result driving firm.

Abdullahi et al. (2019) conducted research on the impact of advertising as a promotional tool on new product development (a case study of Unilever Nigeria plc, Abuja). The aim of this study is to explore the role of advertising as a promotional tool for marketing a new product. A case study of Unilever Nigeria plc. An attempt was made to evaluate the effectiveness or role of advertising as one of the promotional mix element used by Unilever Nigeria Plc Abuja. This study is quantitative in nature as 20 questionnaires were handout to the respondents and nonprobability sampling techniques was adopted, Hypotheses was formulated and tested with the use of Chi-square which shows that there exists relationship between the advertising expenditure and the annual turnover, and that advertising has a significant effect on the development. It also revealed that the choice of the right media selection can affect the effectiveness of the message of advertising.

Josephine et al. (2021). Examined the impact of information technology on poverty alleviation in Nigeria. The peril of poverty in Africa according to UNDP report (1998) tells us about 54 percent of the population is estimated to live in absolute poverty in Africa. In recent years information technology (IT) has emerged as an important instrument to curb poverty in the nation. The objectives to promote information communication technology (ICT) in every economic sector to alleviate poverty, i.e. promote agricultural productions and practice, using ICT to boast productivity are among the enormous considerations in this paper. This research is an attempt to examine the categories, causes and effect of poverty and measures by which poverty can be alleviated using IT. This study relied so much on secondary data. Results have shown that IT has made a great significant difference in the lives of people, and nations globally. For poverty to be totally alleviated a proactive measures lay down by the government and private sector using IT in the areas of economic, quality of life, political stability and provisions of infrastructures shall be enhanced. Proactive measures in the areas of education, health and agriculture etc. can alleviate poverty in Nigeria using the agencies such as National IT Development Agency (NITDA) and GALAZY setup organization to curb these practices.

2.4 Summary and Gap in Empirical Review

Different authors have not written concerning these two variables (entrepreneurship skills and economic development) around the world (see studied Galloway and Brown (2012); and Wang et al. (2013)). However this seminar fills the research gap by using “Financial skills and Networking skills” for Entrepreneurship skills while for economic development “employment generation and Poverty reduction” is used in the research topic “Entrepreneurship skills and economic development in Enugu state”.

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

Research design used in this research is descriptive type of methodology, specifically survey design involving the method of collection of data, analysis and interpretation of data with a view to assess the entrepreneurship skills and economic development in Enugu State, Nigeria.

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3.2 Area of the Study

The study area is in Enugu State of Nigeria. Enugu state is one of the 36 states in Nigeria and is located at the middle of the south east zone. Enugu state is a mono language state where mainly speaks Igbo dialect. The people are industrious in terms business and agriculture. And the research work was limited to the Enugu North, Enugu South and Enugu East Local Government Area of Enugu state. The research was carried out in this area because of the kind of people around those areas.

3.3 Sources of Data

Primary and secondary data were used in the study. Primary data were collected by administering questionnaire to small and medium scale enterprises in Enugu North LGA, furthermore, personal and oral interviews were conducted among the selected firms. While the secondary data are from already made materials of other authors and researchers, like the available relevant textbooks, journals, newspapers and internet.

3.4 Population of the Study

Three main metropolitan areas of Enugu state were used to draw out the population of this seminar work. The study used these areas because, these areas are the heart of industrialization of the Enugu state, small, medium and large enterprises are mainly invested in these areas of the metropolises of the state. The study used Enugu metropolitan area has estimated registered SMEs owners are 2175 according to Enugu SMEs centre record of 2023.

Table 3.1: Enugu Metropolitan SMEs Owners Distribution

LGAs	Business Owners	Percentage (%)
Enugu East LGA	948	44
Enugu South	504	23
Enugu North	723	33
Total	2175	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

3.5 Determination of Sample Size

Taro Yamani’s formula was used to computer the sample sizen = $\frac{N}{1+N(e)^2}$

Where

n =the desired sample size=?

N =population = 2175

e = Maximum acceptable level of error = 5% = 0.05

1 = Constant

The researcher assumed a 5% level of tolerable error hence the sample size was determined as shown below:

Substitute

e = 0.05

Using the formula

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

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$$n = \frac{2175}{1 + 2175(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{2175}{1 + 2175(0.0025)}$$

$$n = \frac{2175}{1 + 5.4375}$$

$$n = \frac{2175}{6.4375} = 337.86$$

∴ n = Sample size = 338 approximately

3.6 Sampling Techniques

The Sampling technique adopted for the selection of respondents was the random sample method because each of the elements has an equal chance of being selected.

3.7 Stratification

To be able to allocate copies of questionnaire proportionally to each stratum, the Kumar proportional allocation formula was used and is shown below: $nh = \frac{nN_h}{N}$

Where n = Sample size

N_h = Population of each stratum

N = Total population

Enugu East LGA

$$\frac{338 \times 948}{2175} = \frac{320424}{2175} = 147$$

Enugu South LGA

$$\frac{338 \times 504}{2175} = \frac{170352}{2175} = 78$$

∴ 56 + 24 = 80

Enugu North LGA

$$\frac{338 \times 725}{2175} = \frac{245050}{2175} = 113$$

3.8 Validity of the Instrument

This simply means the degree to which a test measures what it is supposed to measure. To ascertain the validity of instrument, the questionnaire was given to experts in research fields to test the correlation of the questionnaire to the study. The result showed a positive relationship between the study and the questions.

3.9 Reliability of the Instrument

Reliability of a research instrument concerns the extent to which the instrument yields the same result on repeated trials. To establish the reliability of the instrument, the researcher applied a test retest method.

A pilot group of 20 respondents were issued with the questionnaire, they completed and returned the questionnaire and the results recorded. Two weeks later, the same 20 respondents were again administered same questionnaire and the results recorded. When the two results were compared, they showed high level of reliability.

3.10 Method of Data Presentation and Analysis

The data from the questionnaire were analyzed using frequency tables and simple percentages. Brief analytical comments were used to summarize the findings of those copies of questionnaire as shown in chapter four of this work. Simple percentage formula used will be shown below:

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$$\frac{f}{N} \times \frac{100}{1}$$

Where f = frequency

N = sum of cumulative frequency

The hypotheses were tested using the chi-square statistical tool; given as:

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(o - e)^2}{e}$$

Where \sum = summation sign

o = observed frequency data

e = expected frequency data

Decision Rule: Accept null hypothesis if table value is greater than calculated value, otherwise reject null hypothesis

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Data Presentation

The data is presented on tables and analyzed using inferential statistics.

Table 4.1: Distribution and Return of Questionnaire

LGA	Number of Questionnaire Distributed	ofNumber of Questionnaire Returned	ofNumber ofInvalid Questionnaire	ofNumber ofValid Questionnaire	ValidPercentage (%) of Questionnaire
Enugu North	113	104	2	102	30
Enugu South	78	75	1	74	22
Enugu East	147	126	4	122	48
Total	338	305	7	298	88

Source: Field survey, 2024

Table 4.1 shows that out of 338 copies of questionnaire distributed to the SMEs in the three LGA, 305 copies were returned, representing, 7 copies with 12% of the returned questionnaire were invalid, while 298 copies representing 88% of the returned questionnaire are valid.

4.2 Data Analysis

Table 4.2.1: Financial skills has effect on employment generation in Enugu state, Nigeria

Response Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Very Great extent (VGE)	100	34
Great Extent (GE)	100	34
Low Extent (LE)	50	17
Very Low Extent (VLE)	30	10
Undecided (UD)	18	5
Total	298	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

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Table 4.2.1 above indicated that, 100 respondents representing 34% showed that financial skills had positive effect on employment generation for both VGE and GE, 50 respondents representing 17% for LE, 30 respondents representing 10% indicated VLE, and 18 respondents representing 5% for undecided.

Table 4.2.2: Networking skills had effect poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria

Response Option	No. of Respondents	Percentage (%)
Very Great extent (VGE)	150	50
Great Extent (GE)	100	33
Low Extent (LE)	20	7
Very Low Extent (VLE)	20	7
Undecided (UD)	8	3
Total	298	100

Source: Field Survey, 2024

Table 4.4.2 above show that, 150 respondents representing 50% indicating that the extent networking skills had positive effect on poverty reduction for VGE, 100 respondents representing 33% for GE, 20 respondents representing 7% indicated for LE and VLE, while 8 respondents representing 3% for undecided.

4.3 Test of Hypotheses

The hypotheses were tested using the chi-square statistical tool, which is given as;

$$x^2 = \sum \frac{(o - e)^2}{e}$$

Where: x^2 = chi – square

o = observed frequency

e = expected frequency

Σ = summation sign

Operational Assumptions

Level of significance 5% = 0.05

Degree of freedom (df) = (r – 1) (c – 1)

Where: r = Number of rows

c = Number of columns

df = (2 – 1)(3 – 1)

1 × 2 = 2

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Critical value or table value = 5.991

Decision Rule

If the calculated value of the chi-square (X^2_{cal}) is greater than the table value ((X^2_{tab}) , the H_0 (null hypothesis) is rejected and H_1 (alternative hypothesis) is accepted.

Hypothesis One

H_0 : Financial skills do not have positive effect on employment generation in Enugu state, Nigeria.

In testing this hypothesis, data generated on the adoption of financial skills were regressed with data on employment generation and the result obtained is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1: Financial Skills and Employment Generation

		FS	EG
FS	Pearson Correlation	1.000	.736
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	56	56
EG	Pearson Correlation	.736	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N		56

Source: SPSS Version 22 Window Output

The result presented in Table 1 revealed a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.736, which is positive and close to 1. This suggests that there is a strong positive effect of financial skills on employment generation. The p-value (0.000) which is less than 0.05 level of significance indicates a significant effect. This suggests that of financial skills has a significant effect on employment generation in Enugu state, Nigeria

Hypothesis Two

H_0 : Networking skills does not have positive effect on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

In testing this hypothesis, data generated on the adoption of networking skills were regressed with data on poverty reduction and the result obtained is presented in Table 1 below.

Table 2: Networking Skills and Poverty Reduction

		NS	PR
NS	Pearson Correlation	1.000	.605
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.001
	N	56	56
PR	Pearson Correlation	.605	1.000
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.001	
	N	56	56

Source: SPSS Version 22 Window Output

The result presented in Table 2 revealed a correlation coefficient (R) of 0.605, which is positive and close to 1. This suggests that there is a strong positive effect of networking skills on poverty reduction. The p-value (0.001) which is less than 0.05 level of significance indicates a significant effect. This suggests that networking skills has a significant effect on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

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4.4 Discussion of Findings

4.4.1 Determine the extent to financial skills have effected employment generation in Enugu state, Nigeria

From the first research question one, to what extent does financial skills has effected employment generation in Enugu state, Nigeria? It was found that financial skills have positive effect on employment generation in Enugu State in order wards (see the study, Gary Becker (2017), Human capital theory) and also in line with the above calculation.

4.4.2 Examine the effect of networking skills on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria

Research question two, what extent does networking skills have effected poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria? From the computation above, it was revealed that networking skills have positive effect on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria and is in line with social theory by Jay Barney and Birger Wernerfelt (2011), Resource-Based View (RBV) of entrepreneurship offer different lenses through which we can analyze the relationship between entrepreneurship, and economic development.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Summary of Findings

From the above analyses, the following findings were made:

- i. That financial skills have strong positive effect on employment generation in Enugu state, Nigeria that correlation coefficient (R) of 0.736 and p-value (0.000) which is less than 0.05 level of significance.
- ii. The result from hypotheses II, show the correlation coefficient (R) of 0.605 and the p-value (0.001) which is less than 0.05 level of significance, that networking skills have positive effect on poverty reduction in Enugu state, Nigeria.

5.2 Conclusion

This study concluded that entrepreneurship skills and economic development in Enugu state, Nigeria have positive relationship. But so far, from this research work, shows that entrepreneurship skills have positive effect on economic development in Enugu State, Nigeria from the findings of this study, using financial skills and networking skills for entrepreneurship skills and employment generation and poverty reduction for economic development.

5.3 Recommendations

- i. Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) owners should always engage themselves in seminars on how to improve their financial skills in order to promote employment generation or self-reliance in terms of starting up a business of their own.
- ii. Networking skills should always use in any community or group of people because it reduces the poverty rate in a society or country by people coming together, forming goals and bringing resources together to be used in creating businesses and employment such as cooperative societies and others.

5.4 Contribution to Knowledge

The study on "Entrepreneurship Skills and Economic Development in Enugu State, Nigeria" contributes to knowledge in several ways:

- i. Identifies the key entrepreneurship skills required for economic development in Enugu State, Nigeria.

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- ii. Examines the relationship between entrepreneurship skills and economic development in the state.
- iii. Investigates the impact of entrepreneurship skills on economic indicators such as GDP, employment, and poverty reduction.
- iv. Provides insights into the role of entrepreneurship education and training in enhancing entrepreneurship skills.
- v. Highlights the challenges faced by entrepreneurs in Enugu State and proposes solutions to address them.
- vi. Offers policy recommendations for governments, organizations, and stakeholders to support entrepreneurship development.

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